

Stabilization of soil using sugarcane Bagasse Ash & Polypropylene fibres for Rigid Pavement

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Abstract— In this project we are working on, how to improve overall properties of soil. Soft clay and sandy silty soil are problematic soil from civil engineering construction point of view mainly in rigid pavement construction. To make them extra feasible to production purposes, several substances have been used. This research work gives a hybrid approach of sugarcane bagasse ash and polypropylene fibres to stabilize the clayey soil and sandy silty soil. During experimentation, the rate of bagasse ash varied in 15% and 20%. Likewise, the rate of polypropylene fiber was varied as 1% and 1.5% by weight of soil. We used 2 tests are conducted on soil samples, one is California Bearing Ratio and other is Modified proctor compaction test. The experimental results showing that the combination of sugarcane bagasse ash and polypropylene fibre increases strength at optimum content of 20% and 1% respectively by the weight of soil. The project results proved that the use of this hybrid approach has effectively enhanced the density of soil and CBR values also. The optimum content of SBA and PPF for both the soil are 20% and 1% respectively.

Keywords— Stabilization, Sugarcane Bagasse Ash, Polypropylene Fibre, Modified Proctor Compaction, California Bearing Ratio, Maximum Dry Density

I. INTRODUCTION

Soil is very much essential as foundation for very important part of any civil engineering construction work. That's why we are focusing on strengthening of soil in this project. Load of an any shape is in the long run taken by basis; hence it is very essential to prepare a sufficient robust base for any shape. The system of soil stabilization refers to converting the bodily houses of soil which will improve its electricity, sturdiness, or different features.

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We used 2 type of waste material which are really helpful in stabilization of soil. This are selected according there physical and chemical properties. The materials are Sugarcane bagasse ash and polypropylene fibres. In which sugarcane bagasse ash taken to improve chemical properties of soil.

And the polypropylene fibres are added to increase physical properties of soil.

II. OBJECTIVE

- To reduce thickness of pavement.
- To reduce construction cost of rigid pavement.
- To use of waste material for construction purpose.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. John Paul V, Antony Rachel Sneha M. (2016) They used bamboo fiber on quality conduct of fly ash treated black cotton soil. This paper done on the compaction and quality conduct of fly ash treated expansive soil with bamboo fiber. The ideally fly ash was seen as 20% by load of soil. Bamboo fiber of normal width of 0.45 mm and 25 mm length is used. It was randomly included into the fly ash treated soil at four unique rates of fiber content. The fortified soil tests were conducting unconfined pressure test and compaction tests. It is proven that quality properties of ideal mix of Black cotton soil-fly ash with bamboo filaments is considerably better than untreated black cotton soil

2. Kameshwar Rao Tallapragada, Anuj Kumar Sharma, Tarulata Meshram (2009). They works on benefits of fiber reinforced subgrade. They taken two fibres: nylon fibre and monofilament. The main tests performed were CBR test & UCS Moses G. and Osinubi K. J. (2013) They done their research on compaction efforts of bagasse ash- cement treatment on expansive (black cotton) soil. Cement of varying percentage ie. 0%,2%, 4%,6% and 8% were added with bagasse ash at the rate 0%,2%, 4%,6% and 8% by weight of soil in expansive black cotton soil. All the tests i.e. moisture density relationship, CBR, UCS were performed on the treated soil. The most favorable blend is 4% BA/8% OPC was suggested for the treatment of expansive (black cotton) soil and can be used as a sub-base material

3. test to check the strength. Three proportions were

prepared as 0.75%, 1.5% & 2.25%. Their result shows the CBR value of Black Cotton soil & it also increases considerably due to addition of the fiber in soil. From UCS test it was found that Maximum Stress value of soil increases with increasing aspect ratio of nylon fibre

4. Ken C. Onyelowe (2012) They had done the study on Akwete Lateritic Soil stabilized with cement and Bagasse Ash that was taken from 1.5m below the top layer of soil. In this study soil was stabilized by adding 4% and 6% of cement with the addition of bagasse ash in varying percentage at the rate 0%, 02%,04%, 06%, 08% and 10% by weight of dry soil. After mixing in the soil various tests were performed ie. OMC, MDD and CBR. After sometime it is concluded that with the increase in bagasse ash, OMC also increased. It was observed that the addition of bagasse ash improved the CBR value in compare to the natural soil. MDD reduced at the 4% of cement with bagasse ash in soil whereas MDD increased at 6% of cement content with the increase in the actual percentage of bagasse ash.

5. Kiran R. G. and Kiran L. (2013) They investigates the strength Qualities of Expansive (black Cotton) Soil Utilizing Bagasse ash and Added. substances as for a Stabilizer". Different tests were formed at the various rate of bagasse ash Le. 4%, 8% and 12% and added substance blend extent. It was observed that the above mix proportion showed the change in thickness, CBR and UCD values. For 8% of bagasse ash with 8% cement showed expansion of thickness from 15.16 KN/m² to 16.5 KN/m². At 4% bagasse ash with 08% cement, the CBR values were expanded from 2.13 to 5.43. Similarly

6. M.Heeralal, G.V. Praveen (2011) They Studied the effect of Polypropylene fibre on CKD stabilized soil. The soil they used is Black cotton soil and the various proportions of CKD were 3%, 5%, & 8%. The proportions of PP fibre were taken as 0.25%, 0.50% & 1%. UCS test and CBR test were conducted and the value of both UCS test and CBR test was maximum at CKD content of 8% and fibre content of 1%. So this proportion was considered to be optimum.

7. Nishu verma, Trimurthy narayan pandey, Amit Choudhary, Ujala Mishra (2017) They worked on the effect of bamboo grid reinforcement using in soil with bagasse ash blend. Three bamboo grids (1*1, 2*2, 3*3) were made and lay them in three distinct depths of bagasse ash treated soil sample (1/3,2/3, 3/6). The test performed are CBR test and they found that the increase the CBR by 51% for one layer of bamboo reinforcement, 48% for two- layer of bamboo support and 47% for 3 layers of bamboo fortification. As indicated by CBR resultsq found that the most extreme quality addition is done when soil is mixed with 20% bagasse ash at the depth 2/3 in aperture size 2x2.

8. Pallavi, Pradeep Tiwari, Dr PD Poorey (2016) They studied the stabilization of black cotton soil using fly ash and nylon fibre. In their study, they used different combinations of fly ash as 10%,20%, 30% & 40%. 20% was their optimum value. After which they calculated the optimum value of nylon fibre from various values as0.25%, 0.50%, 0.75%, 1%,

1.5%. From which 0.75% nylon fibre comes to be the optimum. The CBR value of soil+20% fly ash+0.75% fibre was maximum of all other readings. And the MDD was also maximum of this mix proportion.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Tests, Procedures And Results

For Virgin Soil

- Sandy Silty Soil 100%
- Clay Soil 100%

Mixing of Sugarcane Bagasse Ash (SBA) in Each Soil Type of Soil

- Sandy Silty Soil = Replace 15 % of SBA by Weight
- Clay Soil = Replace 15 % of SBA by Weight
- Sandy Silty Soil = Replace 20 % of SBA by Weight
- Clay Soil = Replace 20 % of SBA by Weight

Testing Each Sample

Selection Of Optimum Percentage of SBA in Each Soil. Its taken 20% Sugarcane Bagasse Ash by the Weight of soil.

Mixing Of Polypropylene

FIBRES (PPF) in Each Type of Soil with Optimum Content of SBA

- Sandy Silty Soil + Optimum Content of SBA 20% = Replace 1 % PF
- Clay Soil + Optimum Content of SBA 20% = Replace 1 % of PPF
- Sandy Soil + Optimum Content of SBA 20% = Replace 1.5 % PPF
- Clay Soil + Optimum Content of SBA 20% = Replace 1.5 % of PPF

TESTING EACH SAMPLE

RESULTS

The tables which are showing the result got from Modified Proctor Compaction Test (MDD) and California Bearing Ratio CBR test, for Two different soil are as follows. 18:57

Table 1: Result - Clay Soil (100%)

Sr No.	Sample Description	Test Performed	Unit	Result	Test Method
1	Clay Soil (100%)	Proctor Density (MDD)	Gm/CC	1.552	IS 2720 (Part -8)
2		OMC	%	20.72	
		CBR Test	%	2.56	IS 2720 (Part -16)

Table 2: Result - Clay Soil (100%) + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash

	Sample Description	Test Performed	Unit	Result	Test Method
1	Clay Soil 85% + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash	Proctor Density (MDD)	Gm/CC	1.695	IS 2720 (Part -8)
2		OMC	%	12.56	
		CBR Test	%	3.24	IS 2720 (Part -16)

Figure 1: Result - Clay Soil + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash + PolyPropylene Fibre

Table 3: Result - Clay Soil + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash

Sr No.	Sample Description	Test Performed	Unit	Result	Test Method
1	Clay Soil 80% + Sugarcane Bagasse	Proctor Density (MDD)	Gm/CC	1.714	IS 2720 (Part -8)
2		OMC	%	11.38	
		CBR Test	%	3.36	IS 2720 (Part -16)

Table 4: Result - Clay Soil + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash + PolyPropylene Fibre

Sr No.	Sample Description	Test Performed	Unit	Result	Test Method
1	Clay Soil 80% + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash 20% + Polypropylene Fibre 1%	Proctor Density (MDD)	Gm/CC	1.752	IS 2720 (Part -8)
2		OMC	%	10.25	
		CBR Test	%	4.88	IS 2720 (Part -16)

The maximum dry density of clay soil with bagasse ash from 1.552 gm/cc for virgin soil to 1.695 gm/cc and optimum moisture content decrease from 20.72 % to 12.56 % with sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA) content of 15%. And CBR Value also Increased from 2.56% to 3.24%.

Table 5: Result - Clay Soil + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash + PolyPropylene Fibre

Sr No.	Sample Description	Test Performed	Unit	Result	Test Method
1	Clay Soil 80% + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash 20% + Polypropylene Fibre 1.5%	Proctor Density (MDD)	Gm/CC	1.702	IS 2720 (Part -8)
2		OMC	%	10.99	
		CBR Test	%	4.74	IS 2720 (Part -16)

Increase of PPF into SCBA optimum blend, maximum dry density of clay soil with 20% SCBA. + 1.5% PPF decreased from 1.714 g/cc to 1.702 g/cc and optimum moisture content slightly increased from 10.25% to 10.99%. But the CBR value Slightly decreased from 3.36% to 4.74%.

Table 6: Result - Sandy Silty Soil (100%)

Sr No.	Sample Description	Test Performed	Unit	Result	Test Method
1	Sandy Silty Soil (100%)	Proctor Density (MDD)	Gm/CC	1.641	IS 2720 (Part -8)
2		OMC	%	15.62	
		CBR Test	%	2.94	IS 2720 (Part -16)

The maximum dry density of sandy silty soil with bagasse ash from 1.641 gm/cc for virgin soil to 1.721gm/cc and optimum moisture content decrease from 15.62% to 12.85% with sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA) content of 15% And CBR Value also Increased from 2.94% to 3.13%.

Table 7: Result - Sandy Silty Soil + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash

Sr No.	Sample Description	Test Performed	Unit	Result	Test Method
1	Sandy Silty Soil 85% + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash 15%	Proctor Density (MDD)	Gm/CC	1.721	IS 2720 (Part -8)
2		OMC	%	12.85	
		CBR Test	%	3.13	IS 2720 (Part -16)

Table 8: Result - Sandy Silty Soil + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash

Sr No.	Sample Description	Test Performed	Unit	Result	Test Method
1	Sandy Silty Soil 80% + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash 20%	Proctor Density (MDD)	Gm/CC	1.762	IS 2720 (Part -8)
2		OMC	%	12.58	
		CBR Test	%	3.32	IS 2720 (Part -16)

As the OMC content decreases heavily further addition of SCBA is not needed, the optimum content of Sugarcane bagasse ash in Clay Soil is 20% Considered.

Table 9: Result - Sandy Silty Soil + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash + Poly Propylene Fibre

Sr No.	Sample Description	Test Performed	Unit	Result	Test Method
1	Sandy Silty Soil 80% + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash 20% + Poly Propylene Fiber 1%	Proctor Density (MDD)	Gm/CC	1.795	IS 2720 (Part -8)
2		OMC	%	10.01	
		CBR Test	%	5.42	IS 2720 (Part -16)

Table 10: Result - Sandy Silty Soil + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash + Poly Propylene Fibre

Sr No.	Sample Description	Test Performed	Unit	Result	Test Method
1	Sandy Silty Soil 80% + Sugarcane Bagasse Ash 20% + Poly Propylene Fiber 1.5%	Proctor Density (MDD)	Gm/CC	1.762	IS 2720 (Part -8)
2		OMC	%	10.27	
		CBR Test	%	5.29	IS 2720 (Part -16)

Increase of PPF into SCBA optimum blend, maximum dry density of sandy silty soil with 20% SCBA + 1.5 % PPF decreased from 1.762 gm/cc to 1.762 gm/cc and optimum moisture content slightly increased from 10.01% to 10.27%. But the CBR value slightly decreased from 3.32 % to 5.29 %

CONCLUSION

Sugarcane bagasse ash is a waste product of manufacturing process is can be effectively used in stabilization process of Soil due to its cementitious properties that helps in increasing the strength of soil.

Thus, the optimum mixture of 79% clay soil along with 20% SCBA +1.0% PPF is recommended for successful Stabilization of Clay Soil.

Thus, the optimum mixture of 79% clay soil along with 20% SCBA + 1.0% PPF is recommended for successful stabilization of sandy silty soil.

From this we conclude that, for the successful stabilization of soil the optimum mixture of soil, sugarcane bagasse ash and polypropylene fibre should be 79%, 20% and 1.0% respectively.

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